

**DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF FDG PET FOR PREDICTING CONVERSION FROM
MCI TO ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE**

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table S1. Application of the GRADE System, 2025.

GRADE factor	Analysis Based on Results
1. Risk of Bias	The QUADAS-2 assessment (Figure 2) showed that although many studies had a low risk of bias in the Index Test and Flow and Timing, there was a frequency of “uncertain” or “high” risk in the Patient Selection and Reference Standard categories. This indicates that the way participants were recruited and how the final diagnosis of AD was confirmed may have introduced biases.
2. Inconsistency	Sensitivity varied widely from 44% to 96% and specificity from 44% to 95%. The text also noted significant variability in FDG PET acquisition and processing protocols (scanners, doses, fasting, acquisition time). The ROC curve (Figure 5) shows a notable dispersion of study points relative to the summary curve.
3. Imprecision	The summary ROC curve (Figure 5) provided an estimated AUC of 0.86 with an estimated sensitivity of 78% to a median specificity of 80%. The confidence intervals (95% CI) for the likelihood ratios were: LR+: 3.7 [2.2 – 6.35] and LR–: 0.27 [0.16 – 0.45]. These intervals are relatively narrow (especially the LR–), suggesting a reasonable accuracy of the summary estimates.
4. Indirectness	Not applicable, as the included studies measured the outcome of interest (conversion from MCI to AD) directly in the population of interest (patients with MCI).
5. Publication Bias	The number of included studies (n=10 for the meta-analysis) is small, which increases the risk.

Table S2. Raw data and 2x2 contingency tables for studies included in the meta-analysis.

Study	MCI Stable	MCI > AD	TP	FN	FP	TN
Cao et al., 2023	164	93	41	52	92	72
Choi, 2018	92	79	64	15	17	75
Dukart et al., 2016	265	117	105	12	26	238
Iaccarino et al., 2017	16	14	11	3	3	13
Inui et al., 2017	19	49	47	2	1	18
Ito et al., 2015	47	41	29	12	14	33
Lange et al., 2016	181	60	42	18	54	127
Lu et al., 2018	409	217	173	44	83	326
Pagani et al., 2017	27	95	83	12	3	24
Wang et al., 2016	64	65	45	20	20	44

MCI: mild cognitive impairment

DA: Alzheimer disease